

Economics of 10 Buffalo and Cow: For Establishment of a Dairy in Rural Area

Lokendra^{1*}, Manisha Doot², Rohitash Kumar³

^{1*}M.V.Sc Scholar- Department of Veterinary and Animal Husbandry Extension at College of Veterinary Science & Animal Husbandry, Kamdhenu University, Junagadh, Gujarat

²Ph.D. Scholar- Department of Veterinary Public Health & Epidemiology at College of Veterinary and Animal Science, RAJUVAS, Bikaner, Rajasthan

³Teaching Associate, Pashu Vigyan Kendra, Nagaur, RAJUVAS, Bikaner

Calculating cost and income (Economics) for rearing 10 Cows or Buffaloes under rural conditions

Sr. No.	Content	Unit	Buffaloes	Crossbred Cows
1.	Cost of Animal	Rupees	65,000	70,000
2.	Inter-Calving Interval	Month	15	14
3.	Average Fat	%	7.0	3.7
4.	Lactation Yield (305 day)	Litres	2700	4400
5.	Cost of Fodder	Rs/Quintal	110	110
6.	Cost of Dry Fodder	Rs/Quintal	550	550
7.	Number of Labourers	Man	1	1
8.	Wages of Labour	Rs/day	283	283
9.	Cost of Concentrate	Rs/Quintal	2100	2100
10.	Cost of Breeding	Rs/Animal	2000	2500
11.	Income from Dung	Rs/Animal/Year	1820	1820
12.	Rate of Milk	Rs/Litre	42.0	27.5
13.	Annual Rate of Interest	%	11.0	11.0

14.	Total milk consumption by a calf	Litres	250	250
15.	Calf mortality rate	%	20	20
16.	Male: Female Calf ratio	Ratio	50:50	50:50
17.	Cost of Heifers	Rs	13,000	20,000

Assumptions for calculating economics

Sr. No.	Particulars of Expenditure	10 Buffaloes	10 Crossbred Cows
A. Number of Animals			
1.	Milch Animal	10	10
2.	Calves	4	4
	Total	14	14
B. Capital Cost			
1.	Cost of Animals	6,50,000	7,00,000
2.	Sheds and Stores	3,60,000	4,50,000
3.	Silo-pits	25,000	25,000
4.	Dairy Equipment	1,40,000	1,40,000
	Total	11,75,000	13,15,000
C. Fixed Costs			
1.	Interest on Capital cost (11%)	1,61,563	1,68,758
2.	Depreciation on Animals (5%)	40,625	40,833
3.	Depreciation on Sheds (4%)	18,000	21,000
4.	Depreciation on equipment (6%)	12,375	11,550
5.	Insurance of animals (3%)	24,375	24,500
	Total	2,56,938	2,66,642
D. Current Expenditure			
1.	Expenditure on Green fodder (Rs)	2,01,509	2,06,880
2.	Expenditure on Dry fodder (Rs)	1,11,155	1,06,920

3.	Expenditure on Concentrate fodder (Rs)	2,65,020	2,98,410
4.	Expenditure on Calf feeding (Rs)	42,000	27,500
5.	Wages (Rs)	1,27,500	1,19,000
6.	Veterinary Expenses (Rs)	20,000	25,000
7.	Miscellaneous (Electricity, water & repair) (Rs)	30,000	32,000
	Total	7,94,184	8,15,710
E. Total fixed and current expenditure		10,54,122	10,82,352
F. Cost of milk production/Kg		39.04	24.60
G. Income			
1.	From milk	11,34,000	12,10,000
2.	Appreciation of calves	52,000	80,000
3.	Sale of Farm Yard Manure (FYM)	25,025	23,375
	Total Income (Rs)	12,11,025	13,13,375
	Total Income/Ltr (Rs)	44.85	29.85
H. Total Profit (Rs)		1,56,904	2,31,023
Total Profit/ Year		1,25,535	1,98,020
Total Profit/ Ltr		5.81	5.25